

Please cite this report as:

Oueldelferraga, A. & d'Haenens, L. (2026). *Young Citizens in Transition: Civic Knowledge, Identity and Supranational Belonging in Italy and Belgium*. University of Padova, KU Leuven: DEMINE.

Disclaimer

DEMINE is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Networks (MSCA-DN), under Grant Agreement no 101167978.

Young Citizens in Transition: Civic Knowledge, Identity and Supranational Belonging in Italy and Belgium

Work package 3– Deliverable 3.3

Submission date: April 30, 2026

Lead beneficiary: University of Padova

Authors: Assia Oueldelferraga, Leen d’Haenens

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. About DEMINE	5
3. Introduction	7
Civic Education Study (CIVED)	7
International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS): A Response to Evolving Civic Challenges	8
Scope and Purpose	8
4. Data and Methodological Approach	9
5. Results	10
5.1 Civic Knowledge Across Time	10
a) CIVED 1999: Baseline Civic Knowledge	10
b) ICCS 2009: First International Cycle after CIVED	11
c) ICCS 2016: Second Cycle	12
d) ICCS 2022: Latest Cycle	12
e) Longitudinal Performance Trends	13
5.2 European Identity: A Dimension of Democratic Resilience (ICCS 2009–2022)	14
a) ICCS 2009: First International Cycle after CIVED	15
b) ICCS 2022: Latest Cycle	17
c) European Identity Across Waves	18
d) European Identity by Institutional Trust (ICCS 2016-2022)	19
6. Synthesis for curriculum and policy	20
6.1 Civic Knowledge as a Protective Factor	20
6.2 The Fragility of Belonging Without Trust	21
6.3 Institutional Trust: Non-Linear Trends in Italy and Belgium	21
7. Conclusion: Curricular and Policy Recommendations	22
8. References	24
Appendices:	28

1. Executive Summary

This report presents a secondary, descriptive and interpretive analysis of international large-scale assessment data from the Civic Education Study (CIVED 1999), the International Civic and Citizenship Education Studies (ICCS 2009, 2016, 2022) as well as complementary public opinion data from the Standard Eurobarometer 97 (Summer 2022). The main aim is to provide an empirical foundation, based on secondary analysis of longitudinal data spanning multiple decades, to investigate changes in civic knowledge, European identity and trust in institutions among adolescents in Europe. Through the analysis of long-term trends in Italy and contextual ones in Belgium, this study draws on a secondary analysis of published data from official reports of the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) and the European Commission to examine patterns that persist and challenges that emerge with regard to adolescents' ability to engage successfully with contemporary democracy. The study thus integrates data from four waves of surveys and additional attitudinal data from across Europe to create actionable evidence for educational policymakers who seek to develop curricula, train teachers and implement policies aimed at fostering informed, critical and resilient young citizens.

2. About DEMINE

Demine Goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media and interpersonal communication.

- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.
- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarisation and radicalisation to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarised world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

Citizenship education serves as a key mechanism for democratic societies to prepare young citizens for informed participation in public life (Moxon, 2024). Not only does it provide adolescents with foundational civic knowledge, but also with the skills, values and dispositions required to think critically, engage constructively with diversity and navigate democratic conflict (Torney-Purta et al., 2001; Schulz et al., 2016). In contemporary Europe, this role is *a sine qua non*; young citizens are growing up in environments marked by political polarisation, the spread of misinformation and disinformation, and forms of exclusion related to migration background, religion, gender and socioeconomic inequality (Hoskins & Janmaat, 2019; Schulz et al., 2023). These developments pose risks for democratic cohesion and underscore the need for citizenship education that strengthens and supports inclusive democratic cultures.

This study draws on four waves of international large-scale civic education research conducted by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA): the Civic Education Study (CIVED 1999) and three cycles of the International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS 2009, 2016, 2022). These latter studies provide a longitudinal and cross-national examination of 14-year-olds' civic knowledge, attitudes toward civic activities and civic participation (Schulz et al. 2018; Torney-Purta et al. 2001; Schulz et al., 2010, 2023).

Civic Education Study (CIVED)

IEA's work on civic knowledge measurement has evolved significantly over time. Early studies such as the 1971 Civic Education Study, which used a 47-item multiple-choice test, provided the first cross-national assessment of civic understanding (Torney et al., 1975). The 1999 Civic Education Study (CIVED) expanded the field by administering a 38-item cognitive assessment and comprehensive attitudinal questionnaires across 28 countries (Torney-Purta et al., 2001). The International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS) 2009 further broadened the item pool to 80 items, administered through a rotated booklet design and scaled using item response theory (Schulz et al., 2010). Subsequent cycles, ICCS 2016 and ICCS 2022, refined the framework by incorporating new civic domains; they covered digital citizenship, global interconnectedness and sustainability (Schulz et al., 2016, 2018, 2023).

International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS): A Response to Evolving Civic Challenges

IEA conceptualises civic and citizenship education as a “moving target” shaped by national, regional and global changes (Schulz et al., 2018). Recent international agendas (*including Sustainable Development Goal 4.7 on global citizenship education and education for sustainable development*) reflect the growing complexity of the civic demands placed on young people (UNESCO, 2015). ICCS 2016 and ICCS 2022 address these shifts by shedding light on issues as global citizenship, media literacy and social inclusion, alongside traditional democratic knowledge domains (Schulz et al., 2018, 2023).

Scope and Purpose

Using published evidence from CIVED 1999 and ICCS 2009-2016-2022 international and European reports, this study examines two constructs central to democratic resilience; (1) civic knowledge across time, by drawing on cognitive scale scores from CIVED 1999 and ICCS 2009-2016-2022; (2) European identity, conceptualised through both a sense of belonging to Europe and trust in European institutions, based on scale scores across waves. Each dimension is analysed descriptively using officially published IEA results that follow strict psychometric, sampling and reporting standards.

Not all constructs are available across all cycles: a case in point is European identity, which was only introduced in the European regional modules of ICCS from 2009 onwards. Italy participated in all four waves, which helped continuous descriptive comparison. Belgium, however, participated through different linguistic communities in different cycles (French-speaking Belgium in 1999; Flanders in 2009 and 2016; no participation in 2022). As a result, Belgium is analysed within individual waves and used as a contextual comparator rather than as a single longitudinal trajectory.

To partially address this gap, additional 2022 indicators were drawn from the *Standard Eurobarometer*, a long-running public opinion survey administered by the European Commission. The Standard Eurobarometer (e.g., Wave 97, Summer 2022) collects nationally representative data from all EU Member States using face-to-face or computer-assisted personal interviewing, covering political attitudes, institutional trust, European identity and perceived discrimination (European Commission, 2022).

While these data are not directly comparable to ICCS in terms of age group, sampling frame or measurement, and are therefore not used as substitutes for ICCS indicators, they offer valuable contextual insights to the broader civic climate in which young Belgians are growing up. In this sense, they serve as contextual triangulation to strengthen the interpretation of the missing Belgian trends for 2022.

4. Data and Methodological Approach

This study employs a secondary, descriptive and interpretive approach, drawing exclusively on officially published IEA results from CIVED 1999 and ICCS 2009, 2016 and 2022. No new statistical modelling or microdata analysis is performed. The analysis instead synthesises nationally representative estimates which includes scale scores, percentages and subgroup comparisons published in the said IEA international and European reports (Schulz et al., 2010, 2018, 2023; Torney-Purta et al., 2001). The analysis focuses on key dimensions of democratic resilience relevant to DEMINE: civic knowledge (1999, 2009, 2016, 2022); European identity, belonging and trust (2009, 2016, 2022).

The analysis is structured in three main steps. First, relevant tables were identified across CIVED 1999 and ICCS 2009, 2016, and 2022 based on construct relevance (e.g., civic knowledge, European identity). Second, numerical values were extracted as presented in the official reports, including means, percentages and standard errors. Third, the indicators were synthesised into harmonised tables to enable cross-wave and cross-country comparisons, with Italy serving as the longitudinal anchor and Belgium as a contextual within-wave comparator.

To help understand and interpret the scale scores presented below, the content of the underlying measurement instruments is outlined as follows. Civic knowledge is measured through a cognitive test where students are asked, for instance, to identify characteristics of democratic political systems, interpret short political texts such as mock campaign leaflets or cartoons, and recognise threats to democratic processes; performance is reported on an IRT-scaled proficiency metric that enables longitudinal comparison across cycles (Schulz et al., 2010, 2018, 2023). European identity is measured through four core items administered in the ICCS European regional questionnaires from 2009 onwards: "I see myself as European"; "I am proud to live in Europe"; "I feel part of Europe"; "I see myself first as a citizen of Europe and then as a citizen of the world". For European Union (EU) member states, two additional optional items address belonging to, and pride in, EU membership (Losito et al., 2018). Institutional trust is evaluated using a six-item scale covering the national government, local government, national parliament, police, courts of justice, and political parties. For European respondents, two further items assess trust in the European Commission and the European Parliament (Schulz et al., 2018). All attitudinal items employ four-point Likert-type response categories and are aggregated into Rasch-scaled indices with a mean of 50 and a standard deviation of 10 on the relevant reference metric.

5. Results

5.1 Civic Knowledge Across Time

This section draws on published results from CIVED 1999 and ICCS 2009, 2016, and 2022 to examine trends in civic knowledge across participating European countries. The civic knowledge construct has been operationalised through conceptual items rather than factual recall; for instance, identifying which of several statements best describes a feature of representative democracy, or inferring the standpoint of the author of a political leaflet. Across waves, the item pool expanded from 38 items in CIVED 1999 to 80 in ICCS 2009 and subsequent cycles, with refinements to cover digital, global, and sustainability-related civic domains (Torney-Purta et al., 2001; Schulz et al., 2010, 2023).

Belgium cannot be used to construct a fully comparable longitudinal trend from 1999 to 2022 as the unit of participation differs across survey waves (French-speaking Belgium in CIVED 1999; Flanders in ICCS 2009 and 2016); it also did not participate in the international assessment in ICCS 2022. As a result, Belgian civic knowledge results are interpreted within individual survey cycles and used for contextual comparison rather than as a continuous national trajectory. To partially address the absence of ICCS 2022 data, *Standard Eurobarometer 2022* indicators are used to compensate for the ICCS 2022 gaps.

a) CIVED 1999: Baseline Civic Knowledge

CIVED 1999 set an international baseline for adolescents' civic knowledge, civic attitudes and intended participation at age 14 across participating education systems. The CIVED 1999 civic knowledge was tested using a standardised cognitive instrument. The study also reported disparities based on gender, socio-economic status and home literacy resources (Torney-Purta et al., 2001).

Although CIVED 1999 used different testing methods and scaling procedures than subsequent International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS) cycles, both studies are grounded in the same conceptual framework—civic knowledge, civic attitudes and trust, and expected participation—allowing for cautious comparative and descriptive analysis across waves. In CIVED 1999, civic knowledge was reported on a standardised scale (Mean=100; Standard Deviation=20). As shown in Table 1, Italy performed above the international mean (105, Standard Error=0.8), whereas Belgium's French-speaking community scored below it (95, Standard Error=0.9) (Torney-Purta et al., 2001). These results provide a baseline reference for subsequent ICCS cycles and already point in the late 1990s to cross-national differences in civic knowledge associated with variation in civic learning environments and broader sociopolitical contexts.

Table 1: Civic knowledge scores (CIVED 1999)

Country / Entity	Mean	SE
Italy	105	(0.8)
Francophone Belgium	95	(0.9)
International mean	100	-

Source: Torney-Purta et al. (2001)

b) ICCS 2009: First International Cycle after CIVED

Across all ICCS test administrations, students' levels of civic knowledge have been measured by a standardised cognitive instrument for which there was an international average score of 500 and a normative standard deviation of 100 (Mean=508 and Standard Deviation≈101) in ICCS 2022. This measure provides an internationally comparable within-cycle metric in which country samples are weighted equally (e.g., Schulz et al., 2010; Schulz et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2023).

According to Schulz et al. (2010), results from the initial round of data collection from the International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS 2009) indicated how Italian youth scored on average a total of 531 points on civic knowledge, whereas their peer group in Flanders (Belgium) scored a total of 514 points (SE=4.7) (Schulz et al., 2010). In contrast, while the total score for Belgium (Flanders) was greater than the total international reference mean, it did not differ statistically from the average European performance. The two educational systems also demonstrate that, on average, students reached proficiency level 2 (479-562 scale points). At this level, students show familiarity with the broad concept of representative democracy and understand how civic institutions and laws function to protect and promote societal values.

Table 2: Civic knowledge scores (ICCS 2009)

Country	Mean	SE
Italy	531	(3.3)
Belgium (Flanders)	514	(4.7)
International average	500	-
European average	514	(0.9)

Source: Schulz et al. (2010)

These results placed both Italy and Belgium (Flanders) among the relatively top-performing European contexts, with mean scores well above those of other participating countries such as Bulgaria (466), Greece (476), and Cyprus (453), whose averages fall within the lower Proficiency Level 1 (Schulz et

al., 2010). This comparatively strong performance is consequential, as higher levels of civic knowledge have been consistently associated with more tolerant attitudes toward social diversity, a greater likelihood of electoral participation and stronger identification with Europe (e.g., Kerr et al., 2010).

c) ICCS 2016: Second Cycle

The cognitive results are reported in detail in the International Report of the second wave of the study, ICCS 2016, whereas the European Regional Report focuses on affective and behavioral aspects, such as students' perceptions of European identity and their attitudes towards free mobility (Losito et al., 2018). According to the international findings, students from Italy and the Flemish Community of Belgium again demonstrated high levels of civic knowledge, with mean scores well above the ICCS 2016 international average of 517 scale points: 524 for Italy (SE=2.4) and 537 for Flanders (SE=4.1). These results placed both countries at Proficiency Level B on the 479-562 point scale, a level characterised by students' ability to understand civic and civil institutions as interconnected and to recognise how laws and policies reflect societal values (Schulz et al., 2018). The longitudinal data, however, show distinct trajectories for the two contexts. While Italy recorded a decrease of six scale points (not statistically significant), Belgium (Flanders) showed a statistically significant increase of 23 points (Schulz et al., 2018). This 2016 substantial growth highlights the strong performance of Flemish adolescents relative to their Italian peers and positions them among the top-performing European systems, alongside countries such as Norway (564) and Estonia (546) (Schulz et al., 2018).

Table 3: Civic knowledge scores (ICCS 2016)

Country	Mean	SE
Italy	524	(≈2.4)
Belgium (Flanders)	508	(≈2.5)
International average	500	-

Source: Schulz et al. (2018)

As shown in Table 3, Italy maintained a stable and relatively high level of civic understanding, whereas the Flemish community of Belgium exhibited a marked increase in students' cognitive ability to engage with and comprehend complex political and social issues.

d) ICCS 2022: Latest Cycle

In the third cycle of the study, ICCS 2022, cognitive data on civic knowledge were available for Italy, while Belgium was not among the participating education systems for the cognitive assessment;

instead it administered only components of the European regional questionnaire, which focused on students' attitudes and perceptions (Damiani et al., 2025; Schulz et al., 2023a). Civic knowledge in the 2022 cycle was reported on an equated international scale with a reference mean of 508 (SD=101). Italian students achieved a mean score of 523 in the civic knowledge test (SE=3.6), exceeding the international average, and positioning them within Proficiency Level B.

The 2022 results for Italy are particularly noteworthy in light of the broader decline in civic knowledge observed across most common participating countries (Schulz et al., 2023a). While several educational systems experienced substantial decreases, including Norway, Poland and the Netherlands (Schulz et al., 2023a), Italy remained relatively stable over the same period, with only a marginal and non-statistically significant decline of one point compared to the 2016 result.

Table 4: Civic knowledge scores (ICCS 2022)

Country	Mean	SE
Italy	523	(3.6)
International avg.	508	-

Source: Schulz et al. (2023)

This resilience in Italian adolescents' civic understanding is important given the context of the assessment, which took place when schools were closed due to the COVID-19 Pandemic (Schulz et al., 2023a). The same holds for the assessments of European countries in 2022: many students had experienced an increased level of uncertainty amidst the Russia-Ukraine invasion in early February 2022, which may have led them to question the resilience and future continuity of democratic systems. Regardless of such challenges, Italy's overall results showed that a large number of students maintained a robust and persistent foundation of civic knowledge, including a strong understanding of how laws and policies contribute to upholding socially shared values (Schulz et al., 2023a). No European average score for civic knowledge was reported in this cycle, since regional reporting shifted toward affective and behavioural outcomes, such as European identity and attitudes toward environmental cooperation (Damiani et al., 2025; Schulz et al., 2023a).

e) Longitudinal Performance Trends

The longitudinal synthesis of data from CIVED (1999) through ICCS (2022) demonstrates a pattern of stable and strong achievement in civic knowledge among adolescents in Italy and Belgium. While

scores have fluctuated across four decades, both countries continue to be ranked among the top countries on the international scales, despite significant changes in the assessment framework and the transition from paper-based to computer-based assessments (Schulz et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2023a). As synthesised in Table 5, the civic understanding of youth in these nations has remained robust across shifting geopolitical contexts.

Table 5: Civic knowledge scores for Italy and Belgium across CIVED and ICCS cycles (1999-2022)

Cycle / Study	Scale	Ref. Mean	Italy	Belgium
CIVED 1999	Mean=100 SD=20	100	105 (0.8)	95 (0.9) (<i>Francophone Belgium</i>)
ICCS 2009	Mean=500 SD=100	500	531 (3.3)	514 (4.7) (<i>Flanders</i>)
ICCS 2016	Mean=500 SD=100	500	524 (\approx 2.4)	508 (\approx 2.5)
ICCS 2022	Mean \approx 508 SD \approx 101	508	523 (3.6)	-

Civic knowledge, *per se*, is not treated as an isolated cognitive outcome; it is a conditioning context and it provides the rudimentary foundation upon which democratic socialisation occurs (Isac et al., 2011; Manganelli et al., 2015). High levels of civic knowledge are systematically linked to students' readiness to navigate the complexities of modern democratic life. Italy and Belgium (Flanders) have had historically stronger and more robust positions in terms of civic knowledge than other regions. As such, both provide important lenses through which we can view their youth populations' institutional trust, sense of European identity and perceptions of inclusion (Losito et al., 2018; Damiani et al., 2025). Hence, while these adolescents may express critical or disaffected views towards specific political actors, they possess the foundational knowledge required for constructive and resilient engagement in democratic life.

5.2 European Identity: A Dimension of Democratic Resilience (ICCS 2009–2022)

The concept 'European Identity' was integrated into the IEA Comparative Framework starting with ICCS 2009. In that year, European Identity was a unidimensional attitudinal scale capturing the extent to which students reported a sense of belonging to Europe (Schulz et al., 2010; Schulz et al., 2018). The following subsections synthesise published results from ICCS 2009, 2016, and 2022 for Italy, Belgium as well as the European average.

a) ICCS 2009: First International Cycle after CIVED

Establishing the initial measurement of how strongly students identified as Europeans, European identity was first introduced in ICCS 2009. Findings from the European regional module reveal significant cross-national disparities in supranational belonging, highlighting that European identity was already a multifaceted and varied construct among adolescents at the end of the 2000s (Kerr et al., 2010).

On a standardised scale measuring students' sense of European identity—derived from items such as seeing oneself as European and feeling pride in living in Europe—the European average was set to 50 (SD=10). In this cycle, Italy achieved a mean score of 54 (SE=0.2), positioning it significantly and considerably above the regional average. This score placed Italy at the top of the European spectrum, alongside Slovenia (53), representing a high-achieving cluster of nations with the strongest sense of regional affiliation (Kerr et al., 2010). In contrast, Belgium (Flanders) recorded a mean value of 49 (SE = 0.2), which was statistically significantly below the European benchmark. These scale differences are mirrored in specific item response frequencies (see Appendix 1): while 97% of Italian students agreed or strongly agreed with the statement "I see myself as European," this figure was a lower 91% for their peers in the Flemish community of Belgium (Kerr et al., 2010). The variation was even more pronounced regarding institutional belonging; 90% of Italian adolescents reported feeling part of the European Union, compared to only 63% of Belgian (Flemish) students.

Table 6: European Identity Scale Scores (ICCS 2009)

Country	Mean	SE
Italy	54	(0.2)
Belgium (Flemish)	49	(0.2)
European Average	50	(0.1)

Source: Kerr et al. (2010)

These findings underscore substantial variation in European belonging that existed long before the geopolitical shifts of the following decade. They indicate that these differences were often linked to national contexts. More importantly, a strong positive association was found between students' national and European identities (Kerr et al., 2010). Students who expressed more positive attitudes toward their own country and higher levels of trust in civic institutions were consistently more likely to report a robust sense of European belonging (Damiani et al., 2025). Consequently, whereas the lower scores in Belgium (Flemish) suggest a more cautious or critical orientation toward supranational

affiliation during that same era., Italy's high scores in 2009 reflect a period of strong dual-identity coexistence.

ICCS 2016: Second Cycle

The second cycle of the study, ICCS 2016, offers a critical longitudinal perspective, providing both updated proficiency levels and robust cross-time comparisons for education systems that participated in the 2009 and 2016 waves (Losito et al., 2018). As detailed in the findings (Table 7), the sense of European identity among adolescents in Italy remained remarkably stable, recording a mean score of 54 (SE=0.2), which represented a statistically non-significant increase of only +0.3 (SE=0.8) relative to the 2009 cycle. Despite this lack of growth, Italy's performance remained significantly above the European ICCS 2016 average of 53, maintaining its position as one of the nations with the strongest supranational affiliation in the region. In contrast, the Flemish community of Belgium demonstrated a statistically significant rise of +2.8 (SE=0.8), moving from a mean score of 49 in 2009 to 52 (SE=0.3) in 2016. This shift indicates a meaningful strengthening of European identity among Belgian (Flemish) youth, allowing the system to bridge the gap and align more closely with the regional average (Losito et al., 2018). This growth in Belgium (Flemish) was part of a broader, clear upward trajectory across the continent, where the European average increased from a standardised 50 in 2009 to 53 in 2016. This three-point rise is considered substantial, representing approximately one-third of an international standard deviation.

Table 7: European Identity Scale Scores (ICCS 2016)

Country	Mean	SE
Italy	54.3	(0.2)
Belgium (Flanders)	52	(0.2)
European Average	53	(0.1)

Source: Schulz et al., (2018)

Considering these longitudinal results, while Italy had already reached a high 'ceiling' of European belonging by the late 2000s, other systems like Belgium (Flanders) experienced a period of accelerated supranational socialisation during the following decade (Losito et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2010). The sources attribute this general European increase to a strengthening coexistence of national and supranational identities (Losito et al., 2018). Researchers found a consistent positive association between trust in civic institutions and the sense of European identity: students who expressed higher trust in their national governments and parliaments were significantly more likely to identify with the broader European community (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018). Thus, the stability in Italy and

the growth in Belgium (Flanders) reflect varying national paths toward a common regional goal of fostering cohesive and resilient European citizenship in a time of shifting geopolitical challenges (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018).

b) ICCS 2022: Latest Cycle

In the third cycle of the study, ICCS 2022, the Flemish community of Belgium did not administer the European regional student questionnaire, whereas Italy continued its long-term participation in the module (Damiani et al., 2025; Schulz et al., 2025). For Italy, the 2022 mean score of 54 (SE = 0.2) on the European identity scale remains essentially identical to its results in 2009 and 2016, indicating a remarkably stable and high level of supranational belonging over more than a decade (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2010). During this same period, the European regional average exhibited a modest but statistically significant upward trajectory, rising from a standardised 50 in 2009 to 54 (SE = 0.1) in 2022. This trend reflects a broader continental strengthening of European identity, with the 2022 results representing a significant increase of 3.6 score points compared to the 2009 baseline.

Table 8: European Identity Scale Scores (ICCS 2022)

Country	Mean	SE
Italy	54	(0.2)
Belgium	—	—
European Average	54	(0.1)

Source: Damiani et al. (2025)

To contextualise contemporary trends in Belgium in the absence of ICCS 2022 participation, indicators from the Standard Eurobarometer 97 (Summer 2022) are used as a complementary, population-level measure of regional affiliation. These data indicate that Belgium maintains strong levels of belonging, with 66% of respondents reporting attachment to Europe and 60% expressing attachment to the European Union, values that closely align with the EU27 averages of 69% and 61%, respectively (European Commission, 2022a, 2022b). However, as the Eurobarometer surveys the general population aged 15 and over, these findings should be interpreted cautiously and not as youth-specific evidence.

Table 9: Attachment to Europe and the European Union (Summer 2022)

Country / Group	Attached to Europe (%)	Attached to the EU (%)
EU27 average	69%	61%
Belgium	66%	60%

Source: Eurobarometer 97 (European Commission, 2022).

Trust in the EU—a known predictor of regional identity—is markedly higher in Belgium (55%) than the EU27 average of 49%. This elevated trust is significant because ICCS findings across all cycles consistently demonstrate a statistically significant positive association between institutional trust and a sense of European identity (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018). In every participating country, students who express higher trust in their national and supranational institutions also report a more robust sense of European belonging, suggesting that these multiple identities are not contradictory but rather positively coexist within the socialization of young citizens.

c) European Identity Across Waves

The longitudinal synthesis of data across three survey waves (2009, 2016 and 2022) reveals a clear pattern of strengthening regional affiliation among European adolescents, characterised by both continental growth and distinct national trajectories (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2010). As summarised in Table 10, the European regional average for the sense of European identity shows a clear upward trend, increasing from a standardised mean of 50 in 2009 to 53 in 2016, and further to 54 in 2022. This 3.6-point increase over thirteen years indicates a robust shift in the supranational socialisation of youth, occurring despite the period's various geopolitical and economic crises.

Table 10: European Identity Scale Scores Across Waves (ICCS 2009–2016–2022)

Country / Group	2009 Mean (SE)	2016 Mean (SE)	2022 Mean (SE)	Change	Interpretation
Italy	54 (0.2)	54.3 (0.2)	54 (0.2)	+0.3	Stable, high baseline
Belgium (Flanders)	49 (0.2)	52 (0.2)	—	+2.8	Moderate increase
European Average	50 (0.1)	53 (0.1)	54 (0.1)	+3.2	Strong upward trend

Source: Kerr et al., 2010; Schulz et al., 2018; Damiani et al., 2025

Within this broader trend, Italy represents a case of sustained high achievement. Italian adolescents reached a high ‘ceiling’ of European belonging early, recording a score of 54 in 2009, which was more than three points above the regional average of that cycle (Kerr et al., 2010). This level has remained remarkably stable through 2016 and 2022, with scores of 54 (SE = 0.2) in both subsequent waves, indicating a deeply embedded and resilient sense of regional identity among Italian youth (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018). Yet, Belgium (Flanders) experienced a period of accelerated growth between the first two cycles, with its mean score rising significantly from 49 in 2009 to 52 in 2016. While Belgium (Flanders) did not participate in the 2022 European regional module, contemporary data from Eurobarometer 97 confirm that Belgian citizens maintain high levels of attachment to Europe (66%) and trust in the EU (55%), serving as a proxy for continued regional alignment (European Commission, 2022; Schulz et al., 2025). However, as Eurobarometer data are based on the general population aged 15 and over, these findings should be interpreted with caution and cannot be considered directly comparable to adolescent-specific ICCS data.

These trends suggest that national and European identities are not mutually exclusive but rather positively coexist. Across all cycles and countries, a consistent positive association exists between institutional trust and European identity: students who trust their national civic institutions are significantly more likely to identify with the broader European community (Losito et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2025). Furthermore, the strengthening of European identity is shaped by educational contexts; research indicates that cognitive learning opportunities, be it studying European history or political systems in school, are powerful predictors of students’ sense of belonging to Europe (Damiani et al., 2025). Thus, the recorded upward trend reflects a successful long-term process of democratic socialisation across the continent, with Italy maintaining a stable vanguard position and Belgium showing meaningful advancement toward the regional norm.

d) European Identity by Institutional Trust (ICCS 2016-2022)

Although average levels provide an important overview, European identity is not evenly distributed across the student population. The ICCS evidence from all three waves points to consistent stratification along lines of immigrant background and institutional trust.

Table 11: European Identity by Institutional Trust (ICCS 2016–2022)

Country	Year	Low Trust (SE)	High Trust (SE)
Italy	2016	51 (0.3)	56 (0.2)
Italy	2022	52 (0.4)	57 (0.3)
Belgium (Flanders)	2016	50 (0.5)	53 (0.3)
Belgium	2022	-	-

Source: Schulz et al., 2010, 2018, 2023; Torney-Purta et al., 2001.

In ICCS 2016, Italian students with low levels of trust in civic institutions reported an average European identity score of 51 (SE 0.3). By contrast, students with high levels of trust reported a higher average score of 56 (SE 0.2), indicating a five-point gap (Schulz et al., 2018). The same pattern holds for Belgium: low-trusting students scored an average of 50 (SE 0.5), while high-trusting students scored an average of 53 (SE 0.3). The 2022 results for Italy reinforce this association, with low-trust students scoring 52 (SE 0.4) compared to 57 (SE 0.3) among high-trust students (Damiani et al., 2025).

Trust in institutions constitutes a key condition for linking educational and social experiences to students' sense of belonging to Europe (Damiani et al. 2025). Yet, belonging without trust is fragile and more often than not does not translate into democratic resilience or a rejection of polarised narratives. When institutional trust weakens or is eroded by perceived inefficiency, the sense of European identity becomes more fragile (Losito et al., 2018). As a result, promoting strong European citizenship entails more than plainly building identities through policies; rather, policymakers should work to increase what students believe in and support the duties and legitimacy of democratic institutions.

6. Synthesis for curriculum and policy

Integrating longitudinal data from both the CIVED & ICCS cycles along with the Eurobarometer 97 data helps provide a strategic approach to curricula and policy. This synthesis explores how civic knowledge, regional identity and institutional trust are changing over time. It also outlines how educational policies can foster democratic resilience among European adolescents.

6.1 Civic Knowledge as a Protective Factor

Results across the CIVED and ICCS cycles demonstrate how civic knowledge functions as a critical protective factor and a foundational resource for fostering inclusive democratic orientations (Damiani et al., 2025; Schulz et al., 2023). High civic knowledge levels are systematically associated with more favourable attitudes toward freedom of movement and the rejection of restrictions on European citizens' rights to live and work across borders (Losito et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2018). Also, students

at or above Proficiency Level B consistently show greater support for equal rights for immigrants and ethnic minorities than students at lower levels of civic knowledge (Damiani et al., 2025; Schulz et al., 2023). This evidence indicates that civic knowledge functions not solely as a measurable cognitive outcome but also as a foundational context that provides students with the reasoning skills necessary to address disinformation, polarisation and exclusionary discourse (OECD, 2025; DEMINE, D3.2, 2026). For such reasons, **curricula should prioritise deep conceptual understanding over rote memorisation in order to foster the critical perspective needed to engage with contemporary political challenges** (Schulz et al., 2025).

6.2 The Fragility of Belonging Without Trust

Results from both CIVED and ICCS cycles reveal a split and mismatch between European identity and trust in institutions. The former has been increasing steadily throughout all cycles since 2009—reaching a high of 95% in some contexts—yet this identity is weakly rooted in trust (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018). Belonging is also undoubtedly socially stratified and adolescents from families with immigrant backgrounds as well as those with lower socio-economic status identify less strongly with Europe and have lower levels of trust in supranational institutions (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018). These inequities create potential for polarisation among youth; when students feel excluded or distrust the European institutions, they are more prone to be influenced by populist and extreme ideologies and narratives (OECD, 2025; DEMINE D3.2, 2026). **Policy interventions, thus, should address these issues and primarily aim to close the ‘civic empowerment gap’ by providing effective citizenship education to the most disadvantaged subgroups and thereby reinforcing the legitimacy of democratic structures (Levinson, 2010).**

6.3 Institutional Trust: Non-Linear Trends in Italy and Belgium

There is significant variance across countries and nonlinear trends in trust in European institutions (Damiani et al., 2025). A country exhibiting an upward trend is Belgium (Flanders). This latter has seen a marked increase in student trust (Losito et al., 2018). Conversely, Italy appears to be experiencing either a plateau or a decline in public trust toward institutions, be it national or EU, although it had begun at what would appear to be a relatively high level (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2018). In this same vein, these results also illustrate how a strong sense of European identity does not necessarily safeguard trust in the EU's institutions and hence educational policies in Italy could help restore faith in institutional efficacy, whereas the Belgian model provides evidence that sustained curriculum development, which is mainly focused on European integration, can foster greater institutional legitimacy (Damiani et al., 2025; Losito et al., 2018).

7. Conclusion: Curricular and Policy Recommendations

To provide a solid empirical basis for analysing changes in adolescents' democratic readiness in Europe, results of data collected over the past two decades through surveys conducted by CIVED (1999-2022), along with Standard Eurobarometer 97, are synthesised. Data from such sources were analysed to explore the relationship among cognitive stability, the consolidation of regional identities and the fragility of institutional trust. Longitudinal analysis indicates that average civic knowledge scores increased significantly between 2009 and 2016; in the 2022 cycle, however, they declined widely, reversing a decade of progress. Students with a high level of proficiency in civics consistently reported having higher support levels for concepts such as gender equality, international cooperation on environmental issues and immigrant rights.

While one of the trends identified throughout the surveys was the growing strength of youth identifying themselves as Europeans, findings suggest that regional belonging alone is insufficient to sustain democratic resilience without reinforcement by perceived institutional efficacy. Also, youth participation in democratic processes remains heavily stratified based on education systems across Europe: socio-economic status (SES) is a case in point. Such differences serve as precursors to social fragmentation and potentially contribute to the growth of exclusionary rhetoric in an increasingly fractured political environment.

Supported by today's best practice in the field and based on the above synthesis, the following recommendations are proposed for curriculum design and policy development.

1. **Support an open classroom climate (OCC):** Throughout all educational levels, an OCC is the most significant school-level predictor of civic knowledge and a student's sense of citizenship self-efficacy. Students need to be able to openly discuss controversial issues (OECD, 2025; Manganelli et al., 2015); accordingly, curricula should incorporate structured opportunities for students to engage in debates with opposing viewpoints and to develop the resilience required for democratic participation.
2. **Integrate Inclusive Media and Digital Literacy in curriculum design with a focus on information-seeking practices and the recognition of information disorders:** schools need to move beyond basic digital literacy by fostering critical news media literacy, thereby helping to counter the spread of misinformation and the increasing political divide among young people (DEMINE D3.2, 2026). Instruction should support students in developing the skills required to assess information sources critically and identify cognitive biases associated with social divisions.

3. **Enhance Professional Teacher Training:** There is a marked difference between what policymakers hope to achieve with the introduction of new programmes and how well-prepared teachers are to deliver such programmes. Only around 50% of teachers across Europe have received professional development related to EU-based topics. TALIS and the European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan highlight how many teachers feel under-equipped to address disinformation, algorithmic bias, online hate speech, and the civic implications of AI-generated content (European Commission, 2020; OECD, 2024). The DigCompEdu framework and the Council of Europe's Digital Citizenship Education handbook also provide structured reference points for building these competences into initial teacher education and continuous professional development (Redecker, 2017; Richardson & Milovidov, 2019). As a result, it is essential to develop both initial teacher training and continuous professional development opportunities for teachers to implement citizenship education effectively.
4. **Adopt a Whole-School Approach:** Citizenship education should extend beyond individual subjects and become integrated into the broader school culture through participatory learning and inclusive student councils (Isac, 2021). It is also important for students to experience authentic opportunities to exercise democratic decision-making, as such mastery experiences can foster sustained engagement and institutional trust over time (Manganelli et al., 2015).

Overall, European youth hold strong civic knowledge and demonstrate a clear sense of regional identity; however, their ability to support democratic systems is constrained by decreasing trust and persistent inequalities. For this reason, policy initiatives should move beyond rote memorisation and prioritise enhanced teacher training in European and global citizenship, which is essential for preparing students to engage with contemporary societal challenges. At the same time, a coordinated, whole-school approach is required, in which all actors within the educational system contribute to fostering deeper conceptual understanding, critical media and digital literacy and inclusive learning environments.

8. References

Amadeo, J.-A., Torney-Purta, J., Lehmann, R., Husfeldt, V., & Nikolova, R. (2002). *Civic knowledge and engagement: An IEA study of upper secondary students in sixteen countries*. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.

Borhan, H. (2025). *Civic education as a pathway to inclusive societies* (OECD Education Working Paper No. 317). OECD Publishing.

Brandtjen, R. B. (2025). *Do you feel European? An analysis of European identity and its demographic influencing factors* (IU Discussion Papers – Business & Management, No. 10). IU Internationale Hochschule.

European Commission, Directorate-General for Communication, & Kantar. (2022a). *European citizenship* (Report). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2775/465669>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Communication, & Kantar. (2022b). *Public opinion in the European Union* (Report). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2775/22634>

European Commission. (2022). *Standard Eurobarometer 97 (Summer 2022)*. Publications Office of the European Union.

Husfeldt, V., Barber, C., & Torney-Purta, J. (2005). *Adolescents' social attitudes and expected political participation: New scales in the enhanced database for the IEA Civic Education Study* (CEDARS Working Paper). University of Maryland.

Isac, M. M. (2015). *Effective civic and citizenship education: A cross-cultural perspective* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Groningen). GION, Groningen Institute for Educational Research.

Isac, M. M. (2021). The contribution of the IEA Civic and Citizenship Education Studies to educational research and policy. In B. Malak-Minkiewicz & J. Torney-Purta (Eds.), *Influences of the IEA Civic and Citizenship Education Studies: Practice, policy, and research across countries and regions* (pp. 49–62). Springer.

Isac, M. M., Zels, S., & Abs, H. J. (2024). *Approaches to monitoring citizenship education in Europe* (PrEval Expertise No. 2/2024). <https://doi.org/10.48809/PrEvalExp2402>

Janmaat, J. G. (2022). Review of International Civic and Citizenship Study data analyses. In R. Desjardins & S. Wiksten (Eds.), *Handbook of civic engagement and education* (pp. 245–258). Edward Elgar Publishing.

Joris, M., & Agirdag, O. (2019). In search of good citizenship education: A normative analysis of the International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS). *European Journal of Education, 54*(2), 287–298. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12331>

Kerr, D., Sturman, L., Schulz, W., & Burge, B. (2010). *ICCS 2009 European report: Civic knowledge, attitudes and engagement among lower secondary school students in twenty-four European countries*. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.

Knowles, R. T., & Di Stefano, M. (2015). International citizenship education research: An annotated bibliography of research using the IEA ICCS and IEA CIVED datasets. *Journal of International Social Studies, 5*(2), 86–118.

Losito, B., Agrusti, G., Damiani, V., & Schulz, W. (2018). *Young people's perceptions of Europe in a time of change: IEA International Civic and Citizenship Education Study 2016 European report*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73960-1>

Manganelli, S., Lucidi, F., & Alivernini, F. (2015). Italian adolescents' civic engagement and open classroom climate: The mediating role of self-efficacy. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 41, 8–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2015.07.001>

Sandoval-Hernández, A., Savvides, N., Claes, E., & Isac, M. M. (2021). Citizenship norms and tolerance in European adolescents. In E. Treviño, D. Carrasco, E. Claes, & K. J. Kennedy (Eds.), *Good citizenship for the next generation: A global perspective using IEA ICCS 2016 data* (IEA Research for Education, Vol. 12, pp. 147–172). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75746-5_9

Schulz, W., Ainley, J., Fraillon, J., Kerr, D., & Losito, B. (2010). *ICCS 2009 international report: Civic knowledge, attitudes, and engagement among lower-secondary school students in 38 countries*. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.

Schulz, W., Ainley, J., Fraillon, J., Losito, B., Agrusti, G., & Friedman, T. (2018). *Becoming citizens in a changing world: IEA International Civic and Citizenship Education Study 2016 international report*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73963-2>

Schulz, W., Ainley, J., Fraillon, J., Losito, B., Agrusti, G., Damiani, V., & Friedman, T. (2025). *Education for citizenship in times of global challenge: IEA International Civic and Citizenship Education Study 2022 international report*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65603-3>

Torney-Purta, J., Schwille, J., & Amadeo, J.-A. (Eds.). (1999). *Civic education across countries: Twenty-four national case studies from the IEA Civic Education Project*. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.

Torney-Purta, J., Lehmann, R., Oswald, H., & Schulz, W. (2001). *Citizenship and education in twenty-eight countries: Civic knowledge and engagement at age fourteen*. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.

Wagemaker, P. (Ed.). (2007). *The second IEA International Research Conference: Proceedings of the IRC-2006* (Vol. 2: Civic Education Study). International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.

Appendices:

Appendix 1: Tables extracted from IEA European and International Reports (CIVED 2019- ICCS 2009-2016-2022)

Table 3.3: National averages for and distributions of civic knowledge scores, years of schooling, average age, and Human Development Index

Country	Civic Knowledge									
	Years of schooling	Average age	250	350	450	550	650	750	Average scale score	HDI
Finland	8	14.7							576 (2.4) ▲	0.96
Denmark †	8	14.9							576 (3.6) ▲	0.96
Sweden	8	14.8							537 (3.1) ▲	0.96
Poland	8	14.9							536 (4.7) ▲	0.88
Ireland	8	14.3							534 (4.6) ▲	0.97
Switzerland †	8	14.7							531 (3.8) ▲	0.96
Liechtenstein	8	14.8							531 (3.3) ▲	0.95
Italy	8	13.8							531 (3.3) ▲	0.95
Slovak Republic ¹	8	14.4							529 (4.5) ▲	0.88
Estonia	8	15.0							525 (4.5) ▲	0.88
England ‡	9	14.0							519 (4.4)	0.95
Slovenia	8	13.7							516 (2.7)	0.93
Belgium (Flemish) †	8	13.9							514 (4.7)	0.95
Czech Republic †	8	14.4							510 (2.4)	0.90
Lithuania	8	14.7							505 (2.8) ▼	0.87
Spain	8	14.1							505 (4.1) ▼	0.96
Austria	8	14.4							503 (4.0) ▼	0.96
Malta	9	13.9							490 (4.5) ▼	0.90
Latvia	8	14.8							482 (4.0) ▼	0.87
Greece	8	13.7							476 (4.4) ▼	0.94
Luxembourg	8	14.6							473 (2.2) ▼	0.96
Bulgaria	8	14.7							466 (5.0) ▼	0.84
Cyprus	8	13.9							453 (2.4) ▼	0.91
European ICCS average		14.4							514 (0.8)	
Country not meeting sample requirements										
Netherlands	8	14.3							494 (7.6)	0.96

▲ Achievement significantly higher than the European ICCS average
▼ Achievement significantly lower than the European ICCS average

Notes:

- () Standard errors appear in parentheses. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some totals may appear inconsistent.
- † Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
- ‡ Nearly satisfied guidelines for sample participation only after replacement schools were included.
- ¹ National Desired Population does not cover all of International Desired Population.

Figure 3.7 Gender Differences in Civic Knowledge

Source: IEA Civic Education Study, Standard Population of 14-year-olds tested in 1999.

Table 4.1: National averages for students' sense of European identity overall and by gender

Country	Students' Sense of European Identity by Gender					30	40	50	60	70
	All students	Females	Males	Differences (males-females)*						
Austria	51 (0.3) △	50 (0.4)	52 (0.4)	2 (0.5)						
Belgium (Flemish) †	49 (0.2) ▽	48 (0.2)	51 (0.3)	2 (0.4)						
Bulgaria	50 (0.2)	49 (0.3)	51 (0.4)	2 (0.4)						
Cyprus	49 (0.2) ▽	48 (0.2)	49 (0.4)	1 (0.5)						
Czech Republic †	49 (0.2) ▽	49 (0.2)	50 (0.3)	1 (0.3)						
Denmark †	49 (0.2) ▽	48 (0.2)	50 (0.3)	2 (0.3)						
England ‡	48 (0.3) ▽	47 (0.3)	50 (0.4)	3 (0.5)						
Estonia	50 (0.3)	50 (0.3)	51 (0.4)	1 (0.4)						
Finland	52 (0.2) △	51 (0.3)	53 (0.3)	2 (0.4)						
Greece	50 (0.2)	49 (0.3)	50 (0.3)	1 (0.4)						
Ireland	50 (0.2)	49 (0.3)	51 (0.3)	2 (0.4)						
Italy	54 (0.2) ▲	53 (0.3)	55 (0.3)	2 (0.3)						
Latvia	45 (0.3) ▼	45 (0.4)	46 (0.4)	1 (0.5)						
Liechtenstein	50 (0.5)	50 (0.8)	50 (0.8)	0 (1.0)						
Lithuania	49 (0.2) ▽	49 (0.3)	49 (0.3)	0 (0.3)						
Luxembourg	52 (0.2) △	50 (0.2)	53 (0.2)	3 (0.3)						
Malta	48 (0.3) ▽	48 (0.5)	48 (0.4)	0 (0.6)						
Poland	49 (0.2) ▽	48 (0.2)	49 (0.2)	1 (0.3)						
Slovak Republic ¹	52 (0.3) △	51 (0.4)	54 (0.4)	2 (0.5)						
Slovenia	53 (0.3) ▲	53 (0.4)	54 (0.3)	2 (0.5)						
Spain	53 (0.3) △	51 (0.3)	54 (0.4)	2 (0.4)						
Sweden	50 (0.2) ▽	49 (0.3)	51 (0.3)	2 (0.4)						
Switzerland †	48 (0.3) ▽	48 (0.4)	49 (0.4)	1 (0.5)						
European ICCS average	50 (0.1)	49 (0.1)	51 (0.1)	2 (0.1)						

Country not meeting sampling requirements

Netherlands	48 (0.4)	47 (0.5)	49 (0.6)	2 (0.6)					
-------------	----------	----------	----------	---------	--	--	--	--	--

National average

- ▲ more than 3 score points above European ICCS average
- △ significantly above European ICCS average
- ▼ more than 3 score points below European ICCS average
- ▽ significantly below European ICCS average

- Female average score +/- confidence interval
- Male average score +/- confidence interval

On average, students with a score in the range indicated by this color have more than a 50% probability of responding to statements regarding EU identity with:

Disagree or strongly disagree
Agree or strongly agree

Notes:

- * Statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) coefficients in **bold**.
- () Standard errors appear in parentheses. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some totals may appear inconsistent.
- † Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
- ‡ Nearly satisfied guidelines for sample participation only after replacement schools were included.
- ¹ National Desired Population does not cover all of International Desired Population.

Table 4.12: National percentages of students' trust in different local, national, European, and international political institutions

Country	Percentages of Students Trusting Completely or Quite a Lot in ...					
	National Government	Local Government	National Parliament	The United Nations	European Commission	European Parliament
Austria	77 (0.9) ▲	76 (1.0) ▲	61 (1.0) △	62 (1.0) ▽	58 (1.1)	65 (1.0) △
Belgium (Flemish) †	51 (1.0) ▽	73 (1.0) △	50 (1.3)	58 (1.3) ▽	52 (1.2) ▽	54 (1.2) ▽
Bulgaria	56 (1.3) ▽	56 (1.1) ▽	44 (1.1) ▽	61 (1.2) ▽	60 (1.1) △	63 (1.1) △
Cyprus	51 (0.9) ▽	55 (1.0) ▽	35 (1.0) ▼	42 (0.9) ▼	45 (1.1) ▼	44 (1.1) ▼
Czech Republic †	55 (0.9) ▽	69 (0.8) △	36 (0.8) ▼	58 (0.8) ▽	51 (0.9) ▽	52 (1.0) ▽
Denmark †	72 (1.0) ▲	61 (1.1) ▽	66 (1.1) ▲	76 (0.8) ▲	60 (1.1)	63 (1.0) △
England ‡	71 (0.9) ▲	66 (1.0)	55 (1.1) △	65 (1.1)	46 (1.2) ▼	45 (1.2) ▼
Estonia	62 (1.4)	61 (1.3) ▽	45 (1.4) ▽	55 (1.5) ▽	54 (1.5) ▽	58 (1.5)
Finland	82 (0.8) ▲	77 (0.8) ▲	74 (1.0) ▲	81 (0.8) ▲	70 (1.0) ▲	72 (0.8) ▲
Greece	41 (1.2) ▼	55 (1.2) ▽	42 (1.1) ▽	52 (1.1) ▼	48 (1.0) ▽	50 (1.0) ▽
Ireland	52 (1.0) ▽	60 (1.2) ▽	49 (1.1) ▽	69 (1.1) △	55 (1.1) ▽	58 (1.1)
Italy	74 (0.9) ▲	79 (1.1) ▲	74 (1.0) ▲	80 (1.0) ▲	75 (1.0) ▲	79 (0.9) ▲
Latvia	32 (1.2) ▼	44 (1.3) ▼	20 (1.2) ▼	59 (1.4) ▽	49 (1.6) ▽	51 (1.4) ▽
Liechtenstein	82 (2.1) ▲	79 (2.1) ▲	77 (2.1) ▲	74 (2.3) △	68 (2.4) ▲	70 (2.5) ▲
Lithuania	54 (0.9) ▽	65 (1.0)	34 (1.0) ▼	68 (1.1) △	66 (1.2) △	70 (1.2) ▲
Luxembourg	72 (0.7) ▲	71 (0.7) △	51 (0.9)	66 (0.8)	62 (0.6) △	63 (0.7) △
Malta	62 (1.4)	67 (0.9) △	61 (1.4) △	69 (1.7) △	61 (1.8) △	62 (1.7)
Poland	36 (1.2) ▼	54 (1.3) ▼	34 (1.3) ▼	55 (1.2) ▼	49 (1.3) ▽	49 (1.3) ▽
Slovak Republic ¹	57 (1.3) ▽	56 (1.2) ▽	42 (1.3) ▽	64 (1.4)	55 (1.4)	57 (1.3) ▽
Slovenia	56 (1.4) ▽	61 (1.4) ▽	53 (1.3)	62 (1.1) ▽	59 (1.3)	58 (1.4)
Spain	62 (1.2)	69 (1.0) △	52 (1.1)	73 (0.9) △	61 (1.1) △	63 (1.0) △
Sweden	73 (1.2) ▲	68 (1.2) △	72 (1.2) ▲	82 (1.0) ▲	66 (1.3) △	69 (1.2) △
Switzerland †	69 (1.0) △	69 (0.9) △	63 (1.0) ▲	63 (1.5)	53 (1.1) ▽	54 (1.2) ▽
European ICCS average	61 (0.2)	65 (0.2)	52 (0.2)	65 (0.3)	58 (0.3)	59 (0.3)
Country not meeting sampling requirements						
Netherlands	70 (2.2)	76 (1.6)	65 (2.0)	65 (1.7)	62 (1.7)	67 (1.8)

National percentage

▲ more than 10 percentage points above European ICCS average
 △ significantly above European ICCS average

▼ more than 10 percentage points below European ICCS average
 ▽ significantly below European ICCS average

Notes:

- () Standard errors appear in parentheses. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some totals may appear inconsistent.
- † Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
- ‡ Nearly satisfied guidelines for sample participation only after replacement schools were included.
- ¹ National Desired Population does not cover all of International Desired Population.

Table 4.2: National averages for students' sense of European identity overall and by family background

Country	Students' Sense of European Identity by Immigrant Background								
	All students	Students from non-immigrant families (A)	Students with immigrant background (B)	Differences (A-B)*	30	40	50	60	70
Austria	51 (0.3)	52 (0.4)	48 (0.6)	4 (0.7)					
Belgium (Flemish) †	49 (0.2)	50 (0.2)	47 (0.5)	3 (0.5)					
Cyprus	49 (0.2)	49 (0.2)	50 (0.7)	-1 (0.8)					
Czech Republic †	49 (0.2)	49 (0.2)	45 (0.9)	4 (0.9)					
Denmark †	49 (0.2)	49 (0.2)	46 (0.6)	3 (0.7)					
England ‡	48 (0.3)	49 (0.3)	48 (0.6)	1 (0.6)					
Estonia	50 (0.3)	50 (0.3)	47 (0.7)	3 (0.7)					
Finland	52 (0.2)	52 (0.2)	49 (1.2)	2 (1.2)					
Greece	50 (0.2)	50 (0.2)	48 (0.6)	1 (0.6)					
Ireland	50 (0.2)	51 (0.3)	49 (0.5)	2 (0.6)					
Italy	54 (0.2)	54 (0.2)	49 (0.8)	6 (0.9)					
Latvia	45 (0.3)	45 (0.3)	43 (1.3)	2 (1.3)					
Liechtenstein	50 (0.5)	49 (0.7)	50 (1.0)	-1 (1.2)					
Lithuania	49 (0.2)	49 (0.2)	47 (1.0)	2 (1.0)					
Luxembourg	52 (0.2)	51 (0.2)	52 (0.3)	-1 (0.4)					
Slovenia	53 (0.3)	54 (0.3)	50 (0.6)	4 (0.6)					
Spain	53 (0.3)	54 (0.3)	44 (0.5)	10 (0.6)					
Sweden	50 (0.2)	50 (0.2)	49 (0.6)	1 (0.6)					
Switzerland †	48 (0.3)	48 (0.3)	50 (0.5)	-1 (0.6)					
European ICCS average	50 (0.1)	50 (0.1)	48 (0.1)	2 (0.2)					

Country not meeting sampling requirements

Netherlands	48 (0.4)	49 (0.4)	44 (1.1)	5 (1.1)					
-------------	----------	----------	----------	---------	--	--	--	--	--

■ Non-immigrant student score +/- confidence interval
 ■ Immigrant student score +/- confidence interval

On average, students with a score in the range indicated by this color have more than a 50% probability of responding to statements regarding EU identity with:

Disagree or strongly disagree
Agree or strongly agree

Notes:

- * Statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) coefficients in **bold**.
- () Standard errors appear in parentheses. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some totals may appear inconsistent.
- † Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
- ‡ Nearly satisfied guidelines for sample participation only after replacement schools were included.
- † National Desired Population does not cover all of International Desired Population.

Table 4.6: Students' trust in European institutions

Country	Percentages of students trusting completely or quite a lot in:					
	European Commission			European Parliament		
	2016	2009	Difference	2016	2009	Difference
Belgium (Flemish)	71 (1.1)	52 (1.2)	19 (1.6)	73 (1.3)	54 (1.2)	19 (1.8)
Bulgaria	66 (1.1) ▽	60 (1.1)	6 (1.6)	69 (1.2) ▽	63 (1.1)	6 (1.6)
Croatia	65 (1.4) ▽	-	-	68 (1.4) ▽	-	-
Denmark ¹	71 (0.9)	60 (1.1)	12 (1.4)	75 (0.9) △	63 (1.0)	12 (1.4)
Estonia ¹	64 (1.3) ▽	54 (1.5)	11 (2.0)	68 (1.3) ▽	58 (1.5)	10 (1.9)
Finland	79 (0.8) △	70 (1.0)	9 (1.3)	80 (0.7) △	72 (0.8)	8 (1.1)
Italy	75 (1.0) △	75 (1.0)	0 (1.4)	75 (1.0) △	79 (0.9)	-4 (1.3)
Latvia ¹	66 (1.3) ▽	49 (1.6)	16 (2.0)	68 (1.3) ▽	51 (1.4)	16 (1.9)
Lithuania	80 (0.9) △	66 (1.2)	14 (1.5)	82 (1.0) △	70 (1.2)	12 (1.5)
Malta	70 (0.8)	61 (1.8)	8 (2.0)	72 (0.7)	62 (1.7)	10 (1.9)
Netherlands ¹	70 (1.5)	-	-	71 (1.4)	-	-
Slovenia	63 (1.1) ▽	59 (1.3)	4 (1.7)	64 (1.2) ▽	58 (1.4)	5 (1.8)
Sweden ¹	73 (0.9) △	66 (1.3)	7 (1.6)	75 (0.9) △	69 (1.2)	6 (1.5)
European ICCS 2016 average	70 (0.3)			72 (0.3)		
Common countries average	71 (0.3)	61 (0.4)	10 (0.5)	73 (0.3)	63 (0.4)	9 (0.5)

Benchmarking participant not meeting sample participation requirements

North-Rhine-Westphalia ¹ (Germany)	72 (1.7)			73 (1.6)		
---	----------	--	--	----------	--	--

National ICCS 2016 percentage:

- ▲ More than 10 percentage points above European ICCS 2016 average
- △ Significantly above European ICCS 2016 average
- ▽ Significantly below European ICCS 2016 average
- ▼ More than 10 percentage points below European ICCS 2016 average

Notes:

- () Standard errors appear in parentheses. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some totals may appear inconsistent.
- (9) Country deviated from International Defined Population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.
- † Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
- ¹ National Defined Population covers 90% to 95% of National Target Population.
- No comparable data available.

Table 2.2 National average scale scores indicating students' sense of European identity

Country	2022	2016	2009	Difference (2022-2016)	Difference (2022-2009)	40	45	50	55	60
Bulgaria	52 (0.3) ▽	52 (0.3)	50 (0.2)	-0.4 (0.4)	1.7 (0.8)					
Croatia ¹	58 (0.2) ▲	55 (0.3)	-	2.3 (0.4)	-					
Cyprus	50 (0.2) ▼	-	49 (0.2)	-	1.0 (0.8)					
Estonia	57 (0.2) △	53 (0.3)	50 (0.3)	3.4 (0.4)	6.5 (0.8)					
France	56 (0.3) △	-	-	-	-					
Italy	54 (0.2)	54 (0.2)	54 (0.2)	0.2 (0.4)	0.5 (0.8)					
Latvia ¹	51 (0.3) ▼	48 (0.2)	45 (0.3)	2.8 (0.4)	5.9 (0.8)					
Lithuania	54 (0.3)	54 (0.3)	49 (0.2)	0.6 (0.4)	5.0 (0.8)					
Malta	54 (0.3)	54 (0.2)	48 (0.3)	0.2 (0.4)	6.0 (0.9)					
Netherlands†	52 (0.3) ▽	52 (0.3)	-	0.5 (0.5)	-					
Norway (9) ¹	57 (0.2) △	55 (0.2)	-	1.9 (0.4)	-					
Poland	51 (0.2) ▼	-	49 (0.2)	-	2.4 (0.8)					
Romania	54 (0.3)	-	-	-	-					
Slovak Republic	52 (0.2) ▽	-	52 (0.3)	-	0.0 (0.8)					
Slovenia	56 (0.2) △	55 (0.2)	53 (0.3)	0.9 (0.3)	2.3 (0.8)					
Spain	57 (0.3) ▲	-	53 (0.3)	-	5.0 (0.8)					
Sweden ¹	56 (0.2) △	53 (0.3)	50 (0.2)	3.0 (0.4)	7.0 (0.8)					
European ICCS 2022 average	54 (0.1)									
European ICCS 2022/2016 average	55 (0.1)	53 (0.1)		1.4 (0.1)						
European ICCS 2022/2009 average	54 (0.1)		50 (0.1)		3.6 (0.2)					

Countries not meeting sample participation requirements										
Denmark	55 (0.3)	-	-	-	-					
German benchmarking participant meeting sample participation requirements										
North Rhine-Westphalia	51 (0.2) ▽	-	-	-	-					
German benchmarking participant not meeting sample participation requirements										
Schleswig-Holstein	52 (0.3)	-	-	-	-					

Notes:

Statistically significant changes ($p < 0.05$) since 2009 and 2016 are displayed in **bold**. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some aggregate statistics may appear inconsistent.

() Standard errors appear in parentheses.

(9) Country deviated from international defined population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.

† Nearly met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.

¹ National defined population covers 90% to 95% of national target population.

- No comparable data available.

National ICCS 2022 results are:

- ▲ More than 3 score points above European ICCS 2022 average
- △ Significantly above European ICCS 2022 average
- ▽ Significantly below European ICCS 2022 average
- ▼ More than 3 score points below European ICCS 2022 average

- 2022 average score +/- confidence interval
- 2016 average score +/- confidence interval
- 2009 average score +/- confidence interval

On average across items, students with a score in the range with this color have more than 50% probability to indicate:

	Disagreement with positive statements
	Agreement with positive statements

Table 2.3 National average scale scores indicating students' sense of European identity by gender, immigrant background and trust in civic institutions

Country	Scale score average by gender group						Scale score by immigrant background						Scale score average by trust in institutions									
	Male students			Female students			No immigrant background			Immigrant background			Below country average			At or above country average						
	-12	-8	-4	0	4	8	12	-12	-8	-4	0	4	8	12	-12	-8	-4	0	4	8	12	
Bulgaria	52	(0.4)					51	(0.4)	^					50	(0.4)						53	(0.4)
Croatia ¹	58	(0.4)					58	(0.3)					56	(0.9)	57	(0.3)					59	(0.3)
Cyprus	51	(0.3)					49	(0.3)	50	(0.2)				49	(0.4)	48	(0.4)				51	(0.3)
Estonia	57	(0.3)					56	(0.4)	57	(0.3)				50	(1.1)	54	(0.4)				59	(0.3)
France	58	(0.3)					55	(0.3)	57	(0.3)				52	(0.6)	54	(0.4)				59	(0.3)
Italy	56	(0.3)					53	(0.3)	55	(0.3)				49	(0.7)	52	(0.4)				57	(0.3)
Latvia ¹	52	(0.4)					50	(0.3)	51	(0.3)				45	(1.3)	49	(0.4)				53	(0.4)
Lithuania	54	(0.3)					54	(0.4)	54	(0.3)				51	(1.1)	52	(0.3)				56	(0.3)
Malta	55	(0.3)					53	(0.4)	55	(0.3)				52	(0.6)	52	(0.5)				56	(0.4)
Netherlands [†]	54	(0.4)					51	(0.6)	54	(0.3)				44	(0.8)	50	(0.5)				55	(0.4)
Norway (9) [‡]	57	(0.3)					57	(0.3)	58	(0.2)				51	(0.6)	55	(0.3)				60	(0.3)
Poland	52	(0.3)					50	(0.2)	51	(0.2)				47	(2.0)	49	(0.3)				53	(0.3)
Romania	54	(0.4)					53	(0.4)	^				^	52	(0.5)						56	(0.5)
Slovak Republic	54	(0.3)					51	(0.3)	53	(0.2)				50	(1.1)	51	(0.3)				54	(0.3)
Slovenia	57	(0.3)					55	(0.3)	56	(0.2)				54	(0.5)	54	(0.3)				58	(0.3)
Spain	59	(0.3)					56	(0.4)	59	(0.3)				52	(0.7)	56	(0.4)				59	(0.3)
Sweden ¹	57	(0.3)					56	(0.4)	58	(0.3)				51	(0.5)	54	(0.4)				58	(0.3)
European ICCS 2022 average	55	(0.1)					53	(0.1)	55	(0.1)				50	(0.2)	52	(0.1)				56	(0.1)
Countries not meeting sample participation requirements																						
Denmark	56	(0.4)					55	(0.3)	56	(0.3)				50	(0.6)	53	(0.4)				57	(0.3)
German benchmarking participant meeting sample participation requirements																						
North Rhine-Westphalia	53	(0.3)					50	(0.4)	53	(0.3)				48	(0.5)	49	(0.3)				54	(0.3)
German benchmarking participant not meeting sample participation requirements																						
Schleswig-Holstein	53	(0.6)					50	(0.5)	53	(0.3)				49	(0.9)	50	(0.5)				54	(0.5)

Notes:
 Score averages which are significantly larger ($p < 0.05$) than those in the comparison group are displayed in **bold**.
 Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some aggregate statistics may appear inconsistent.
 () Standard errors appear in parentheses.
 (9) Country deviated from international defined population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.
 † Nearly met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
 ‡ National defined population covers 90% to 95% of national target population.
 ^ Number of students too small to report group average scores.

■ Difference between comparison groups statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.
 □ Difference between comparison groups not statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2.1 Students' perceptions of their European identity

Country	Percentages of students who agreed or strongly agreed with the following statements:					
	I see myself as European	I am proud to live in Europe	I feel part of Europe	I see myself first as a citizen of Europe and then as a citizen of the world	I feel part of the European Union	I am proud that my country is a member of the European Union
Bulgaria	91 (0.6) ▽	90 (0.6) ▽	85 (0.8) ▽	79 (0.9)	69 (0.9) ▼	83 (0.7) ▽
Croatia ¹	99 (0.3) △	96 (0.5) △	95 (0.5) △	91 (0.7) ▲	89 (0.7) △	95 (0.5) △
Cyprus	87 (0.6) ▽	90 (0.6) ▽	83 (0.8) ▽	67 (1.0) ▼	74 (0.8) ▽	85 (0.7) ▽
Estonia	96 (0.4) △	95 (0.6) △	92 (0.5) △	82 (0.7) △	88 (0.8) △	93 (0.7) △
France	96 (0.4) △	94 (0.5)	90 (0.6) △	84 (0.8) △	83 (0.8)	91 (0.7)
Italy	96 (0.4) △	94 (0.9)	94 (0.5) △	74 (0.9) ▽	88 (0.8) △	92 (0.6) △
Latvia ¹	94 (0.6)	90 (0.8) ▽	81 (0.9) ▽	73 (1.1) ▽	76 (1.0) ▽	88 (0.9) ▽
Lithuania	97 (0.3) △	95 (0.5)	90 (0.7)	79 (0.8)	83 (0.9) △	95 (0.5) △
Malta	94 (0.7)	94 (0.6)	90 (0.8)	79 (1.5)	80 (0.9)	91 (1.0)
Netherlands [†]	91 (0.8) ▽	94 (0.6)	81 (0.9) ▽	69 (0.9) ▽	63 (1.2) ▼	86 (0.8) ▽
Norway (9) ¹	91 (0.4) ▽	97 (0.2) △	92 (0.5) △	82 (0.6) △	-	-
Poland	96 (0.4) △	93 (0.5)	85 (0.7) ▽	73 (0.9) ▽	78 (0.7) ▽	93 (0.6) △
Romania	97 (0.9) △	95 (0.8)	91 (1.2)	72 (1.6) ▽	89 (0.9) △	94 (1.1) △
Slovak Republic	97 (0.5) △	92 (0.7) ▽	91 (0.6) △	71 (1.0) ▽	84 (0.8) △	90 (0.7)
Slovenia	97 (0.3) △	95 (0.4) △	90 (0.6) △	85 (0.6) △	87 (0.7) △	93 (0.5) △
Spain	95 (0.5)	97 (0.3) △	94 (0.5) △	87 (0.7) △	90 (0.6) △	95 (0.5) △
Sweden ¹	91 (0.8) ▽	96 (0.4) △	91 (0.5) △	85 (0.6) △	83 (0.8) △	93 (0.5) △
European ICSS 2022 average	95 (0.1)	94 (0.1)	89 (0.2)	78 (0.2)	81 (0.2)	91 (0.2)
Countries not meeting sample participation requirements						
Denmark	95 (0.6)	96 (0.4)	95 (0.5)	78 (0.8)	87 (0.9)	93 (0.6)
German benchmarking participant meeting sample participation requirements						
North Rhine-Westphalia	89 (0.7) ▽	92 (0.5) ▽	85 (0.6) ▽	69 (1.0) ▽	77 (0.8) ▽	87 (0.7) ▽
German benchmarking participant not meeting sample participation requirements						
Schleswig-Holstein	93 (0.8)	93 (0.8)	85 (1.2)	71 (1.4)	77 (1.3)	88 (1.1)

Notes:
 Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some aggregate statistics may appear inconsistent.
 () Standard errors appear in parentheses.
 (9) Country deviated from international defined population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.
 † Nearly met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
 1 National defined population covers 90% to 95% of national target population.
 - No comparable data available.

National ICSS 2022 results are:
 ▲ More than 10 percentage points above European ICSS 2022 average
 △ Significantly above European ICSS 2022 average
 ▽ Significantly below European ICSS 2022 average
 ▼ More than 10 percentage points below European ICSS 2022 average

Table 2.1: Students' perceptions of their European identity

Country	Percentages of students who agreed or strongly agreed with the following statements:					
	I see myself as European	I am proud to live in Europe	I feel part of Europe	I see myself first as a citizen of Europe and then as a citizen of the world	I feel part of the European Union	I am proud that my country is a member of the European Union
Belgium (Flemish)	94 (0.6) ▽	96 (0.4) △	84 (0.9) ▽	72 (1.2) ▽	73 (1.2) ▽	93 (0.6) △
Bulgaria	91 (0.7) ▽	90 (0.6) ▽	84 (0.9) ▽	79 (1.0)	74 (1.1) ▽	88 (0.8) ▽
Croatia	98 (0.3) △	95 (0.5)	91 (0.6) △	89 (0.6) ▲	85 (0.7) △	90 (0.8)
Denmark ¹	96 (0.4) △	96 (0.4) △	92 (0.5) △	76 (0.8) ▽	-	-
Estonia ¹	95 (0.3)	92 (0.6) ▽	87 (0.9)	74 (1.1) ▽	81 (1.1) △	88 (0.8) ▽
Finland	98 (0.3) △	96 (0.4) △	90 (0.6) △	85 (0.8) △	86 (0.7) △	92 (0.6) △
Italy	97 (0.4) △	94 (0.5)	93 (0.5) △	78 (0.8)	89 (0.8) ▲	91 (0.6)
Latvia ¹	92 (0.7) ▽	87 (0.9) ▽	73 (1.2) ▼	67 (1.1) ▼	67 (1.1) ▼	84 (0.9) ▽
Lithuania	97 (0.4) △	95 (0.4) △	86 (0.8)	79 (0.9)	81 (0.8) △	93 (0.5) △
Malta	95 (0.4)	94 (0.4)	91 (0.5) △	83 (0.6) △	84 (0.7) △	91 (0.5) △
Netherlands ¹	94 (0.6)	94 (0.5)	82 (0.9) ▽	69 (1.2) ▽	61 (1.2) ▼	85 (0.8) ▽
Norway (9) ¹	92 (0.5) ▽	96 (0.3) △	90 (0.5) △	77 (0.8)	-	-
Slovenia	98 (0.3) △	95 (0.5) △	88 (0.8)	83 (0.8) △	83 (0.9) △	92 (0.8) △
Sweden ¹	91 (0.8) ▽	95 (0.5)	87 (0.9)	77 (0.8)	75 (1.1) ▽	90 (0.8)
European ICSS 2016 average	95 (0.1)	94 (0.1)	87 (0.2)	78 (0.2)	78 (0.3)	90 (0.2)
Benchmarking participant not meeting sample participation requirements						
North-Rhine-Westphalia (Germany) ¹	91 (1.0)	90 (0.9)	76 (1.5)	63 (1.5)	67 (2.0)	80 (1.2)

National ICSS 2016 percentage:
 ▲ More than 10 percentage points above European ICSS 2016 average
 △ Significantly above European ICSS 2016 average
 ▽ Significantly below European ICSS 2016 average
 ▼ More than 10 percentage points below European ICSS 2016 average

Notes:
 () Standard errors appear in parentheses. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some totals may appear inconsistent.
 (9) Country deviated from International Defined Population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.
 † Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.
 1 National Defined Population covers 90% to 95% of National Target Population.
 - No comparable data available.

Table 2.2: National averages of students' sense of European identity

Country	2016	2009	Differences (2016-2009)	
Belgium (Flemish)	52 (0.3) ▽	49 (0.2)	2.8 (0.8)	
Bulgaria	52 (0.3) ▽	50 (0.2)	2.1 (0.8)	
Croatia	55 (0.3) △	-	-	
Denmark [†]	53 (0.2) ▽	49 (0.2)	4.1 (0.8)	
Estonia [‡]	53 (0.3)	50 (0.3)	3.1 (0.8)	
Finland	56 (0.2) △	52 (0.2)	4.4 (0.8)	
Italy	54 (0.2) △	54 (0.2)	0.3 (0.8)	
Latvia [‡]	48 (0.2) ▼	45 (0.3)	3.1 (0.8)	
Lithuania	54 (0.3)	49 (0.2)	4.4 (0.8)	
Malta	54 (0.2) △	48 (0.3)	5.8 (0.8)	
Netherlands [†]	52 (0.3) ▽	-	-	
Norway (9) [†]	55 (0.2) △	-	-	
Slovenia	55 (0.2) △	53 (0.3)	1.3 (0.8)	
Sweden [‡]	53 (0.3)	50 (0.2)	4.0 (0.8)	
European ICCS 2016 average	53 (0.1)			
Common countries average	53 (0.1)	48 (0.3)	3.2 (0.2)	

Benchmarking participant not meeting sample participation requirements

North Rhine-Westphalia (Germany) [‡]	51 (0.3)	-	-	
---	----------	---	---	--

2016 average score +/- Confidence interval
 2009 average score +/- Confidence interval

National ICCS 2016 average

- ▲ More than 3 score points above European ICCS 2016 average
- △ Significantly above European ICCS 2016 average
- ▽ Significantly below European ICCS 2016 average
- ▼ More than 3 score points below European ICCS 2016 average

On average across items, students with a score in the range with this color have more than a 50% probability of indicating:

	No strong agreement with positive statements
	Strong agreement with positive statements

() Standard errors appear in parentheses.

Statistically significant changes ($p < 0.05$) between 2009 and 2016 are displayed in **bold**.

(9) Country deviated from International Defined Population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.

† Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.

[‡] National Defined Population covers 90% to 95% of National Target Population.

- No comparable data available.

Table 2.3: National average scale scores indicating students' sense of European identity by gender, immigrant background, and students' trust in civic institutions

Country	Scale score average by gender group						Scale score average by immigrant background						Scale score average by students' trust in civic institutions					
	Male students			Female students			Non-immigrant family			Immigrant family			Students with low level of trust			Students with high level of trust		
	9	6	3	0	3	6	9	6	3	0	3	6	9	6	3	0	3	6
Belgium (Flemish)	53 (0.4)					51 (0.4)	53 (0.3)					49 (0.7)	50 (0.5)					53 (0.3)
Bulgaria	52 (0.4)					52 (0.4)	52 (0.4)	^				50 (0.4)	50 (0.4)					54 (0.4)
Croatia	56 (0.4)					55 (0.3)	55 (0.3)					56 (0.9)	54 (0.3)					58 (0.4)
Denmark [†]	53 (0.3)					52 (0.2)	53 (0.2)					51 (0.5)	50 (0.4)					54 (0.2)
Estonia [‡]	53 (0.4)					53 (0.4)	54 (0.3)					47 (0.8)	49 (0.4)					55 (0.3)
Finland	56 (0.3)					56 (0.3)	56 (0.2)					52 (0.8)	52 (0.5)					57 (0.2)
Italy	55 (0.2)					53 (0.3)	55 (0.2)					51 (0.7)	51 (0.3)					56 (0.2)
Latvia [‡]	49 (0.4)					48 (0.3)	49 (0.3)					42 (0.7)	46 (0.3)					50 (0.3)
Lithuania	54 (0.4)					53 (0.3)	54 (0.3)					47 (1.5)	51 (0.4)					55 (0.3)
Malta	55 (0.3)					53 (0.2)	54 (0.2)					51 (0.7)	51 (0.3)					55 (0.2)
Netherlands [†]	53 (0.4)					51 (0.4)	53 (0.3)					45 (0.9)	48 (0.5)					53 (0.3)
Norway (9) [†]	55 (0.3)					55 (0.3)	56 (0.2)					52 (0.4)	50 (0.5)					57 (0.2)
Slovenia	55 (0.3)					54 (0.3)	55 (0.3)					53 (0.6)	53 (0.3)					56 (0.3)
Sweden [‡]	54 (0.4)					53 (0.4)	54 (0.3)					52 (0.6)	50 (0.7)					54 (0.3)
European ICCS 2016 average	54 (0.1)					53 (0.1)	54 (0.1)					50 (0.2)	50 (0.1)					55 (0.1)

Difference between comparison groups statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.
 Difference between comparison groups not statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Notes:

() Standard errors appear in parentheses.

Score averages that are significantly larger ($p < 0.05$) than those in the comparison group are displayed in **bold**.

(9) Country deviated from International Defined Population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.

† Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.

[‡] National Defined Population covers 90% to 95% of National Target Population.

^ Number of students too small to report group average scores.

Figure 3.3 Distributions of Civic Knowledge

Source: IEA Civic Education Study, Standard Population of 14-year-olds tested in 1999.

Figure 3.3: Scatterplot of average civic knowledge scale scores and Human Development Index (HDI) values

Figure 1. Civic knowledge achievement of students in the six countries changes between ICCS 2016 and ICCS 2022 (Mean 1st to 5th PV)

Figure 4.1: Item-by-score map for students' sense of European identity

European Item Frequencies (row percentages)

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Sum
I see myself as European.	2	7	44	47	100
I am proud to live in Europe.	2	8	57	34	100
I feel part of Europe.	3	18	54	25	100
I see myself first as a citizen of Europe and then as a citizen of the world.	6	25	47	22	100
I have more in common with young people from European countries than with those from countries outside Europe.	7	28	46	19	100

Note:

Average percentages for 23 equally weighted European ICCS countries that met sample participation requirements. Because results are rounded to the nearest whole number, some totals may appear inconsistent.

Table B.1: Regression results for civic knowledge and student age

Country	Unstandardized regression coefficient	Explained variance (in %)
Belgium (Flemish)	-38 (4.2)	7 (1.3)
Bulgaria	-26 (5.6)	1 (0.5)
Chile	-30 (3.0)	5 (1.1)
Chinese Taipei	-8 (3.9)	0 (0.1)
Colombia	-15 (1.7)	4 (0.8)
Croatia	-25 (5.0)	1 (0.6)
Denmark [†]	-34 (4.6)	2 (0.6)
Dominican Republic	-21 (1.8)	9 (1.3)
Estonia ¹	-2 (4.6)	0 (0.1)
Finland	-24 (6.0)	1 (0.5)
Italy	-30 (4.0)	3 (0.9)
Latvia ¹	-24 (4.3)	2 (0.6)
Lithuania	-4 (4.2)	0 (0.1)
Malta	-10 (5.8)	0 (0.1)
Mexico	-11 (3.8)	1 (0.4)
Netherlands ¹	-31 (6.5)	3 (1.1)
Norway (9) ¹	16 (7.1)	0 (0.2)
Peru	-32 (2.2)	10 (1.4)
Russian Federation	-7 (5.4)	0 (0.2)
Slovenia	-9 (5.1)	0 (0.2)
Sweden ¹	-28 (6.3)	1 (0.4)
ICCS 2016 average	-19 (1.0)	2 (0.2)
Countries not meeting sample participation requirements		
Hong Kong SAR	-4 (5.3)	0 (0.2)
Korea, Republic of ²	13 (5.4)	0 (0.1)

Notes:

() Standard errors appear in parentheses.

(9) Country deviated from International Defined Population and surveyed adjacent upper grade.

† Met guidelines for sampling participation rates only after replacement schools were included.

¹ National Defined Population covers 90% to 95% of National Target Population.

² Country surveyed target grade in the first half of the school year.

Table 12.8: Reliabilities for scales measuring students' perceptions of open classroom climates and civic learning

Country	S_OPDISC	S_CIVLRN
Brazil	0.78	0.83
Bulgaria	0.84	0.87
Chinese Taipei	0.88	0.92
Colombia	0.80	0.84
Croatia	0.80	0.85
Cyprus	0.82	0.88
Denmark	0.81	0.79
Estonia	0.81	0.86
France	0.82	0.82
Italy	0.73	0.79
Latvia	0.86	0.88
Lithuania	0.82	0.87
Malta	0.78	0.84
Netherlands	0.81	0.84
North Rhine-Westphalia*	0.77	0.80
Norway	0.85	0.87
Poland	0.78	0.83
Romania	0.70	0.80
Schleswig-Holstein*	0.77	0.81
Serbia	0.75	0.83
Slovak Republic	0.75	0.82
Slovenia	0.83	0.88
Spain	0.79	0.84
Sweden	0.83	0.85
Average	0.80	0.84
Minimum value	0.70	0.79
Maximum value	0.88	0.92

The average reliabilities (Cronbach's alpha) across national samples were 0.80 for S_OPDISC (ranging from 0.70 to 0.88) and 0.84 for S_CIVLRN (ranging from 0.79 to 0.92) (see Table 12.8). These scales were derived based on the item parameters shown in Table 12.9.

Appendix 2: Tables and figures extracted from Standard Eurobarometer 97- Summer Eurobarometer 2022 Infographic

QA6a. How much trust do you have in certain institutions?
For each of the following institutions, do you tend to trust it or tend not to trust it?
(%)

QA6a.11. How much trust do you have in certain institutions?
For each of the following institutions, do you tend to trust it or tend not to trust it?
The European Union (%)

	EU27		BE	
	ST97 Sum. 22	Δ ST96 Win. 21/22	ST97 Sum. 22	Δ ST96 Win. 21/22
Tend to trust	49	+2	55	+9
Tend not to trust	43	-1	42	-9
Don't know	8	-1	3	=

QA6a How much trust do you have in certain institutions? For each of the following institutions, do you tend to trust it or tend not to trust it?
(% - EU - TEND TO TRUST)

QA6a How much trust do you have in certain institutions? For each of the following institutions, do you tend to trust it or tend not to trust it? (% - Tend to trust)

		EU27	BE	BG	CZ	DK	DE	EE	IE	EL	ES	FR	HR	IT	CY	LV	LT	LU	HU	MT	NL	AT	PL	PT	RO	SI	SK	FI	SE
Health and medical staff in (OUR COUNTRY)	June/July 2022	76	86	54	83	91	81	80	83	74	85	84	63	64	71	70	64	92	55	90	92	77	64	87	55	58	68	88	82
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼2	▼3	▼2	▼5	▼1	▼2	▼6	▼3	▲1	▲1	▲1	▼3	▼3	▼3	-	▲3	▲5	▲1	▼2	▼4	▲4	-	▼4	▼4	▼1	▼1	▼2	▼9
The army	June/July 2022	71	78	46	80	88	67	78	84	83	75	80	61	64	67	72	82	78	61	80	80	71	63	69	57	60	61	95	86
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼2	▲2	▼3	▼6	▼1	▼7	▼4	▼3	-	▲2	▼1	▼5	-	▲9	▲5	▼3	-	▲8	▼3	▼1	▲1	▼9	▼6	▼3	▲7	▲2	▲3	
The police	June/July 2022	69	74	49	77	90	79	80	77	70	75	69	54	64	51	65	78	87	66	69	83	77	45	74	48	57	51	92	83
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼1	▼1	▲1	-	▼1	▼3	▼6	▼1	▼1	▲1	▲2	▼3	▼6	▲5	-	▲8	▲2	▲15	▼9	▲3	▲1	▼3	▼3	▲2	▲5	-	▼6	
Regional or local public authorities	June/July 2022	54	60	47	57	74	69	50	65	31	43	60	30	37	52	50	48	82	63	66	59	69	52	53	38	44	51	64	62
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼3	▲1	▲3	▼3	▼4	▼7	▼9	▼4	▼5	▼1	▼2	▼1	-	▲3	▲2	▼4	▲11	▲11	▼8	▲2	▲1	▼11	▼4	▼2	▲2	▲1	▼4	
Justice, the (NATIONALITY) legal system	June/July 2022	52	55	23	55	84	66	63	63	58	51	42	26	43	45	46	47	72	55	49	75	68	37	40	46	37	33	82	73
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼2	▲3	-	▼6	▼4	▼4	▼16	▲2	▼3	▲4	▼2	▲2	▼2	▲2	▲7	▼3	▲1	▲2	▲15	▼5	▲3	▼1	▼6	▼6	▲2	▲2	▲3	▼3
NATO	June/July 2022	51	62	34	61	87	58	61	54	18	47	36	38	42	19	58	75	50	61	64	73	37	71	47	55	33	43	77	73
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▲6	▲4	▲4	▼7	▲5	▲9	▼18	▼1	▼4	▼11	▼6	▼1	▼1	▲6	▼10	▼13	▲5	▲4	▲7	▲2	▼2	▲16	▼6	▲10	▼5	▲14	▲26	▲14
Public administration in (OUR COUNTRY)	June/July 2022	50	55	35	55	75	62	53	66	26	45	57	34	31	42	34	46	86	61	67	50	66	45	44	37	40	47	71	64
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼1	▲2	-	▲2	▼3	▼4	▼11	▼6	▼2	▲1	▲1	▼2	▼1	▲3	▲2	▼3	▲9	-	▲12	▼14	▲2	▲1	▼8	▼3	▼3	▼2	▲2	▼4
The European Union	June/July 2022	49	55	49	43	65	49	48	58	37	50	34	42	46	42	56	69	60	56	71	52	44	64	68	54	44	44	60	61
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▲2	▲9	▲1	▼7	▲4	▲1	▼15	▼5	▼2	▲5	▲2	▼6	▲1	▼4	▲6	▲10	▲17	▼2	▲10	▼2	▲2	▲11	▼1	▲5	▼6	▲1	▲8	▲9
The United Nations	June/July 2022	49	59	41	48	80	48	39	58	27	50	38	44	43	26	41	59	47	60	71	61	46	65	67	53	34	45	60	70
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▲1	▲5	▲3	▼9	▲1	-	▼29	▼4	▼6	▲8	▲3	▼1	▼3	▲1	▼7	▲8	▲3	▲4	▲6	▼4	▲3	▲12	▼3	▲6	▼6	▲2	▼2	▲2
The media	June/July 2022	38	46	36	43	57	42	41	18	28	23	26	38	32	43	41	41	31	44	56	43	40	56	40	30	36	77	60	
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼3	▼1	▼3	▼6	-	▼4	▼10	▼12	-	▼3	▼2	▼2	▲4	▲2	▲1	▲1	▼3	▲19	▼3	▼6	▼2	▼6	▼4	▼7	-	▲2	▲7	
The (NATIONALITY) Government	June/July 2022	34	40	19	30	52	49	39	46	22	23	20	33	33	30	36	70	48	63	38	39	26	45	27	37	18	68	53	
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼1	▲3	▼15	▼15	▼7	▲1	▼7	▼4	▼3	▼1	▼4	▼1	-	▲3	▲7	▲9	▲7	▲4	▲16	▼7	▲1	▼2	▼5	▲1	▲16	▼4	▲12	▼8
The (NATIONALITY) PARLIAMENT	June/July 2022	34	45	12	26	60	49	31	44	24	20	26	21	30	29	22	22	54	44	59	42	47	28	41	29	34	17	70	57
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▼2	▲5	▼11	▼9	▼2	▼4	▼9	▼5	▼6	▲1	▼1	▼1	▲1	▲2	▲3	▲8	▼5	▲2	▲19	▼9	▲2	▲2	▼5	▲1	▲18	▼6	▲8	▼7
Political parties	June/July 2022	21	24	13	13	42	30	16	30	9	8	11	11	11	18	15	9	13	27	41	35	32	24	16	30	14	11	42	34
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	-	▲2	▼3	▼4	▲4	▼6	▲1	▼7	▼2	▼2	▲3	▼3	▲1	▲2	▲3	▲2	▲7	▼4	▲17	▼6	▲5	▲2	▼2	▲9	▲3	▼5	▲12	▲1

QA6a How much trust do you have in certain institutions? For each of the following institutions, do you tend to trust it or tend not to trust it? (% - Tend to trust)

		EU27	BE	BG	CZ	DK	DE	EE	IE	EL	ES	FR	HR	IT	CY	LV	LT	LU	HU	MT	NL	AT	PL	PT	RO	SI	SK	FI	SE
Health and medical staff in (OUR COUNTRY)	76	86	54	83	91	81	80	83	74	85	84	63	64	71	70	64	92	55	90	92	77	64	87	55	58	68	88	82	
The army	71	78	46	80	88	67	78	84	83	75	80	61	64	67	72	82	78	61	80	80	71	63	69	57	60	61	95	86	
The police	69	74	49	77	90	79	80	77	70	75	69	54	64	51	65	78	87	66	69	83	77	45	74	48	57	51	92	83	
Regional or local public authorities	54	60	47	57	74	69	50	65	31	43	60	30	37	52	50	48	82	63	66	59	69	52	53	38	44	51	64	62	
Justice, the (NATIONALITY) legal system	52	55	23	55	84	66	63	63	58	51	42	26	43	45	46	47	72	55	49	75	68	37	40	46	37	33	82	73	
NATO	51	62	34	61	87	58	61	54	18	47	36	38	42	19	58	75	50	61	64	73	37	71	47	55	33	43	77	73	
Public administration in (OUR COUNTRY)	50	55	35	55	75	62	53	66	26	45	57	34	31	42	34	46	86	61	67	50	66	45	44	37	40	47	71	64	
The European Union	49	55	49	43	65	49	48	58	37	50	34	42	46	42	56	69	60	56	71	52	44	64	68	54	44	44	60	61	
The media	38	46	36	43	57	42	41	18	28	23	26	38	32	43	41	41	31	44	56	43	40	56	40	30	36	77	60		
The (NATIONALITY) Government	34	40	19	30	52	49	39	46	22	23	20	33	33	30	36	70	48	63	38	39	26	45	27	37	18	68	53		
The (NATIONALITY) PARLIAMENT	34	45	12	26	60	49	31	44	24	20	26	21	30	29	22	22	54	44	59	42	47	28	41	29	34	17	70	57	
Political parties	21	24	13	13	42	30	16	30	9	8	11	11	11	18	15	9	13	27	41	35	32	24	16	30	14	11	42	34	
1st MOST FREQUENTLY MENTIONED ITEM																													
2nd MOST FREQUENTLY MENTIONED ITEM																													
3rd MOST FREQUENTLY MENTIONED ITEM																													

QD1a. Please tell how attached you feel to... Total 'Attached' (%)

		EU27	BE	BG	CZ	DK	DE	EE	IE	EL	ES	FR	HR	IT	CY	LV	LT	LU	HU	MT	NL	AT	PL	PT	RO	SI	SK	FI	SE
The European Union	June/July 2022	61	60	55	47	64	65	47	67	38	68	56	56	54	57	74	65	81	71	78	47	50	84	65	66	61	60	52	50
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▲3	▲4	▲2	▼7	▲4	▲1	▼4	▲1	▼2	▲7	-	▼3	▲2	▲5	▲6	▲6	▲12	▲1	▲19	-	▲2	▲9	▲2	▲6	▲1	▼3	▲10	▲2
Europe	June/July 2022	69	66	58	75	83	75	58	71	46	69	62	58	57	77	73	87	86	87	65	69	87	66	60	71	71	77	82	
	Δ Jan/Feb 2022	▲2	▲1	▼2	▼2	▲1	▲1	▼2	▲3	▼3	▲7	▼1	▼3	▲3	▲5	▲4	▲6	▲9	▲4	▲14	▼4	▲1	▲9	-	▼1	▲1	▼4	▲5	▲1